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The Role of Financial Technology in Promoting Financial Inclusion and Stimulating Pakistan's Economic Growth

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the relationship between financial technology (FinTech), financial inclusion, and economic growth in Pakistan, with a focus on GDP, ICTs, digital literacy, and education. It employs Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach on quarterly data for the period 1996 to 2022. The findings reveal that both in the short and long run, financial technology enhance the country's economic growth, while digital illiteracy hampers it. Increased education expenditures prove beneficial for boosting economic growth in both time frames. Conversely, insufficient investment in information and communication technologies negatively affects economic growth in the short run, and a low uptake of regulatory quality has a detrimental impact in the long run. These results offer valuable policy implications for fostering equitable growth and sustainable development in Pakistan, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive adoption and utilization of financial technology.

Keywords: Financial technology; Economic growth; Information technology; Regulatory quality; Education expenditures; ARDL technique; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fintech is revolutionizing financial services and products and becoming a worldwide economic powerhouse due to its innovative use of technology. Fintech has transformed global money management and shopping via innovations in evidence technology, data analytics, and mobile assembly. Fintech has enhanced financial services accessibility and efficiency, innovation and productivity, and financial inclusion, all of which boost economic growth, according to several studies. Financial technology may transform economies worldwide (Danladi et al. 2023). Despite substantial studies in China, Bangladesh, and Indonesia, Pakistan's economic progress has yet to receive much attention. Due to its rapidly changing financial environment and developing digital infrastructure, Pakistan is an excellent case study for Fintech and economic development. Pakistani businesses, financial institutions, and governments must understand Fintech adoption and economic progress (Zaidi & Shah, 2023). Stakeholders in Pakistan may use Fintech to address local concerns and opportunities to boost sustainable development, job creation, and poverty reduction. Other developing countries aiming to harness tech-driven innovation for inclusive development and prosperity might benefit from Pakistan's Fintech experience (Iftikhar, 2022). The ever-changing Fintech and ICT infrastructure of Pakistan is crucial to its economic growth and development. With its investments in ICT infrastructure, including mobile penetration, internet access, and digital payment systems, Pakistan is setting itself up for Fintech to disrupt the financial sector and drive inclusive growth. Pakistan's ICT infrastructure has made significant strides, thanks to the concerted efforts of the government and private sector, as well as the widespread adoption of mobile devices (Zaheer, 2023).

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The rise of smartphones and internet usage is opening doors for Fintech solutions to enhance financial services for the underrepresented. Fintech, combined with Pakistan's ICT infrastructure, may solve some of its biggest financial issues, such as low financial literacy, cash transactions, and difficulty accessing conventional banking services (Wahga et al. 2023). Fintech technologies may boost economic growth and reduce poverty by offering secure, affordable, and accessible financial services via digital platforms and mobile devices. While Fintech holds immense promise, Pakistan is grappling with several technical, regulatory, and social hurdles that demand immediate attention. Ensuring internet safety, fostering innovation through regulation, and enhancing digital literacy and financial technology confidence are crucial steps towards overcoming these obstacles (Nnaomah et al. 2024).

Pakistan has a compelling opportunity to address its energy issues and generate sustainable economic growth at the intersection of Fintech and renewable energy. Pakistan's growing urban population, rapid industrialization, and dependency on fossil fuels make its energy infrastructure vulnerable to supply outages. It is exciting to see renewable energy initiatives leveraging Fintech to promote energy accessibility, investment, and climate change mitigation. Pakistan has abundant solar, wind, and hydroelectric power, but it is underutilized (Ali & Ahmed, 2023). Insufficient infrastructure, regulatory impediments, and finance have hindered renewable energy adoption, restricting our capacity to diversify our energy sources and reduce our dependence on fossil fuels. Fintech businesses have devised innovative financial solutions to overcome these constraints and accelerate Pakistan's renewable energy transition (Amin et al. 2023). Fintech's use of digital platforms, blockchain technology, and peer-to-peer financing allows for cheap renewable energy project finance, simplified investment processes, and decentralized energy systems. Fintech can make energy markets more transparent, responsible, and efficient, attracting investors and consumers. Fintech and renewable energy demand may boost Pakistan's economy, ecology, and society. Technology-driven financial innovation may help Pakistan access sustainable energy, create jobs, reduce poverty, and combat climate change (Hussain et al. 2023).

This study examines FinTech service acceptability and impact in Pakistan from several perspectives to understand its complicated dynamics. Its focus is on how FinTech services have helped Pakistan's economy and financial inclusion. By studying how FinTech innovations may enhance financial services, entrepreneurship, and economic production, we can better comprehend their effects on socioeconomic development. Alongside this broad topic, the research examines how Pakistan's regulatory structure affects FinTech adoption and impact. This inquiry examines FinTech regulatory frameworks that govern operations, licensing, and compliance to identify policy imperatives and regulatory bottlenecks affecting the ecosystem. It also examines how regulatory dynamics affect Pakistan's financial sector's market entry, innovation diffusion, and FinTech acceptance. Digital literacy, FinTech service usage, and their implications in Pakistan are also examined. This study examines how digital literacy affects FinTech uptake, usage, and socioeconomic outcomes. It acknowledges that technology adoption requires digital literacy. This study examines the relationships between digital literacy programs, educational interventions, and financial technology (FinTech) to inform policy interventions to promote digital inclusion and socioeconomic empowerment in Pakistan.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

The study examines how Fintech has boosted Pakistan's economy, given the above criteria. To maximize Fintech's contribution to Pakistan's economic growth, the study analyzes regulatory frameworks, infrastructure, and consumer behaviour to make practical recommendations for fostering its innovation. Further, the study focuses on financial technology and ICT infrastructure in Pakistan. It examines Pakistan's ICT infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, and Fintech adoption patterns to assess the pros and cons of using technology-driven innovation to boost economic growth and financial inclusion. By analyzing relevant literature, empirical data, and stakeholder perspectives, the study aims to advise policymakers, regulators, financial institutions, and Fintech entrepreneurs on how to use technology to achieve sustainable and inclusive growth in Pakistan. At last, this study investigates the relationship between renewable energy demand in Pakistan and financial technology. It analyzes renewable energy markets, Fintech trends, and regulatory frameworks to enhance investment and acceptability and find technology-driven solutions to opportunities and issues. The more visibility of the research objectives of the study is as follows:

Objective 1: To examine the relationship between financial technology (FinTech) adoption and financial inclusion in Pakistan and determine how it contributes to economic growth.

Objective 2: To analyze the regulatory environment for FinTech in Pakistan and evaluate its impact on financial inclusion and economic growth, as well as identify potential areas for improvement.

Objective 3: To investigate the role of digital literacy in promoting FinTech adoption and usage in Pakistan, and to develop strategies for addressing digital literacy gaps to support financial inclusion and economic growth.

The stated research objectives have been empirically tested through time series cointegration technique.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review is divided into different aspects the study, including financial inclusion, financial infrastructure, information

technology, education, and economic growth.

2.1. Financial inclusion and Economic Growth Nexus

The complicated interaction between financial technology (Fintech), banking sector dynamics, and economic growth and inclusion has been studied in many contexts. Duramany-Lakkoh et al. (2022) studied Sierra Leone's economic growth and emphasized banking sector indicators such as bank liquidity reserve, domestic lending to private sectors, and interest rate spread. Li and Zhang (2022) study the United States' economic growth and bank development before and after the 2008 financial crisis, concentrating on two-way causality and short-term consequences. Álvarez-Gamboa et al. (2023) examine financial inclusion in Ecuador and its impact on the nation, while Bekele and Degu (2023) examine sub-Saharan Africa and financial inclusion, respectively. Both findings emphasize the need for equitable financial services for long-term viability. Zaagha (2023) examines how monetary policy affects Nigerian insurance companies to understand financial markets and policy dynamics. According to Anjum and Veermanju (2023), blockchain technology may improve financial sector efficiency and security, demonstrating the revolutionary potential of emerging technologies. Wanof (2023) and Alsmadi et al. (2023) examine how digital technology innovation and Fintech adoption affect banking services and financial access in low-income settings and Malaysia, respectively, highlighting the potential for inclusive development and regulatory adaptation. In addition, Nsiah and Tweneboah (2023) examine if any factors affect financial inclusion in Africa. Income, institution quality, and private-sector domestic loans are their priorities. Edo et al. (2023) use machine learning to study Fintech acceptability and performance, whereas Marei uses Trust and Environment (TOE) frameworks. Finally, studies from Pakistan (Rehman et al., 2023) and Malaysia (Ahmad & Yahaya, 2023) examine how blockchain, Big Data, and mobile banking affect bank credit to SMEs and adoption of mobile banking, respectively.

The literature has extensively investigated how financial technology (Fintech) affects economic performance, sustainability, and organizational dynamics. Sunardi and Tatariyanto (2023) examine how COVID-19 and Fintech have influenced business performance and capital sufficiency in Indonesian government banking. Capital sufficiency moderates the relationship between Fintech adoption and financial performance, highlighting the complex relationship between regulatory capital demands and technology innovation. Their findings show that Fintech adoption somewhat improves financial performance. The COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh has led Guang-Wen and Siddik (2023) to study the relationship between Fintech, Green Finance, Green Investment, and Environmental Performance. They found that fintech adoption significantly impacts GF, GI, and EP, making it essential to green finance and sustainable economic development. Siddik et al. (2023) use ecological modernization theory and a resource-based viewpoint to examine how Fintech and FL affect sustainable performance in the Bangladeshi textile industry. Their study shows that FL and Fintech adoption improves sustainability performance, demonstrating Fintech's revolutionary potential to enhance social and environmental outcomes. Huang et al. (2023) indicate that FinTech adoption reduces credit constraints, promotes entrepreneurship, and reduces the adverse effects of economic uncertainty on household consumption. Cumming et al. (2023) examine Fintech's impact on global business and how capital-raising tools like crowdfunding and peer-to-peer lending promote entrepreneurial globalization. Hong et al. (2023) develop and explore a new Fintech adoption indicator at the firm level in connection to product market competitiveness, emphasizing the dynamic interplay between competitive dynamics and technology adoption in business behaviour. Last but not least, Yahaya et al. (2023) analyze Fintech adoption by enterprises using the UTAUT framework. Their study demonstrates that performance expectation, effort expectancy, social effect, and customer trust are significant elements in Fintech adoption, which may help firms increase performance.

These studies provide a more complicated picture of how broad Fintech adoption may affect consumer behaviour, organizational dynamics, sustainability, and economic growth.

2.2. Regulatory Environment and ICTs Exports Nexus

Reviewing about how financial sector dynamics affect economic and environmental performance may help explain the complex link between financial development, governance frameworks, and sustainable development goals. Ofori et al. (2023) highlight the complicated relationship between financial metrics, economic governance, and environmental quality in the BRICS, MINT, and G7 nations by evaluating their association. Sou and Vinnicombe (2023) examine government, FDI, and tourist demand. Through FDI accumulation, the government indirectly impacts tourist demand, underlining the importance of government frameworks in economic outcomes. Gerged et al. (2023) examine how GCC governance influences corporate environmental disclosure. This study illuminates macro-level environmental reporting methods and sustainability. Liu et al. (2023) analyze the effects of environmental taxes, governance, and energy prices on OECD countries' environmental quality better to understand tax and governance policy reforms for environmental sustainability. Hoppe et al. (2023) introduce the Tax Complexity Index (TCI), a measure of corporate income tax system complexity, to assess how the regulatory environment affects multinational corporations' tax decisions and policy discussions. Bisset (2023) examines the complex relationship between institutional governance, government performance, environmental deterioration, and governance indices in South Africa. In their 2023 study of Asian domestic institutions'

environmental performance, Nadeem et al. emphasize the impact of global value chains, governance facilitation, and policy aims. Sinha et al. (2023) outline an energy transition policy framework that supports sustainable development by tackling socioeconomic inequities and enhancing governance. Zarei et al. (2023) propose an index for groundwater sustainable management in Iran's aquifers, highlighting economic, social, and institutional elements. Mateev et al. (2023) examine how ownership and regulation affect risk-taking in MENA banks to understand better how regulatory frameworks affect market discipline and financial stability. Finally, Olaiya et al. (2023) examine how financial inclusion affects GDP growth in Nigeria, emphasizing the role of non-bank financial institutions in reaching particular populations and promoting economic development. Ahmed (2022) summarizes the revolutionary impact of electronic financial services in India's financial environment, focusing on business growth and savings and investment distribution.

Environmental problems, economic development, and financial technology (Fintech) literature examines the evolving financial services environment, technological advances, and sustainability aspects. Zhou et al. (2023) analyze how climate change and natural disasters affect banking, insurance, and capital markets, highlighting their vulnerability. Their study emphasizes income levels, regulatory frameworks, and adaptive strategies to mitigate climate-related threats to financial stability and investor confidence. Alsmadi et al. (2023) attribute Fintech's transformation in Malaysia's banking sector to government initiatives, digital payment systems, and regulatory support. Their study shows how Fintech may reform banks and enhance financial services, which might boost innovation and economic growth. Macha and Massawe (2023) critique Tanzania's Fintech business, highlighting regulatory issues and growth potential. Infrastructure, institutional support, and regulatory frameworks all help Fintech expand, according to their study. Kimani (2023) examines how the COVID-19 pandemic affects Kenyan bank lending, shedding light on credit allocation and the government's response to economic turmoil. The study showed that prudent regulations and regulatory measures help stabilize the financial system and boost private-sector lending. Anjum and Veermanju (2023) examine the revolutionary potential of AI and BC in banking by concentrating on efficiency, cost savings, and security. Their analysis of AI applications and BC technology advancement shows how new technology affects financial services and organizational structures. Ceci and Razzaq (2023) examine how renewable energy, environmental policies, and ICTs affect G10 resource depletion. Their results illuminate how digitization and environmental governance might improve sustainability.

These studies bridge gaps in our understanding of financial technology, environmental dangers, and economic growth and illuminate the possibilities and challenges scholars, practitioners, and policymakers confront in today's internationally linked economy.

2.3. Digital Literacy and Education Expenditures

Digital inclusion, technology adoption, and literacy studies show that ICTs drive socioeconomic development, literacy, and digital abilities. Asongu, Odhiambo, and Rahman (2023) examined IT, income inequality, and adult literacy in developing countries. They said that school internet access initiatives boost adult literacy. Their study suggests that fair growth requires enhancing educational infrastructure and addressing digital disparities. Samsuddin et al. (2021) examines how rural Malaysians read digitally, illustrating how ICTs may assist bridge the digital divide and empower rural people. Their analysis emphasizes the necessity for targeted digital literacy and rural development ICT initiatives. Saleh's (2021) study on Lebanon's literate adults' skills gap emphasizes the need of 21st-century skills including communication and critical thinking in this age of technology. The research stresses the need for collaboration to overcome the skills gap and equip workers for the digital age. Fute, Wan, and Oubibi (2023) note that literacy is essential for socioeconomic prosperity and calls for a global effort to ensure that all people can read, write, and perform basic arithmetic by 2030. Their research emphasizes the need to sponsor literacy and education programs to assist adults and children in overcoming socioeconomic hurdles. Deen-Swarray (2016) analyses how literacy rates impact ICT adoption in African countries, finding that greater literacy rates lead to increased ICT usage. The report emphasizes the need to increase literacy rates to achieve digital inclusion and take advantage of ICTs' revolutionary capacity for social and economic growth.

Many aspects of development and sustainability literature give insights into policymaking and decision-making. Putera et al. (2022) assess Indonesia's scientific literacy and culture development via its roots and policy frameworks. Global literacy development measures show areas for improvement, and the study stresses institutional support and government action to increase scientific literacy. Mahalik, Mallick, and Padhan (2021) explain the complicated relationship between education and environmental quality in BRICS countries and how primary and secondary education reduces carbon emissions. Their study suggests that switching to renewable energy and investing in universities might assist developing nations' environments over time. Agesa and Agesa (2020) help us understand Sub-Saharan African birth spacing preferences by studying ex-ante plans to spread out births. Their study shows that city living increases the period between children, informing policymakers about socioeconomic issues that affect fertility. Tinta's (2023) study on energy substitution dynamics in Africa explains the renewable energy transition. Human capital and institutional quality are crucial to energy transitions, and the study offers suggestions for sustainable development

initiatives throughout the continent. Ibrahim and Ajide (2021) propose carbon-reduction policies based on BRICS energy usage and trade openness. Their findings suggest promoting cleaner energy sources and improving regulatory quality to achieve environmental sustainability. Yu (2021) and Wang et al. (2021) analyze the environmental implications of urbanization, focusing on China and how government policies and foreign investment might enhance the environment. Their study on the relationship between economic growth, environmental protection, and urban development informs urban planning and management policy. Ha, Dang Le, and Trung-Kien (2021) illuminate the complex relationship between urbanization and poverty in Vietnam, contributing to poverty reduction literature. Human capital and gross regional domestic product reduce poverty, while government spending and export value may not. Song, Seo, and Lee (2023) examine logistics efficiency, industrialization, urbanization, and carbon dioxide emissions to give thorough information on transportation modes and their environmental impacts. Policymakers may utilize the study's results to promote sustainable logistics and decrease transportation's environmental impact. Last but not least, Bansak and Starr (2021) investigate how the COVID-19 pandemic has influenced K-12 distance learning and the challenges children and their families have had in adapting. Their findings emphasize the importance of educational inputs and teacher-student connections for crisis-related learning.

Based on the given literature, the following are the research hypotheses of the study, i.e.,

Hypothesis 1: Greater adoption of FinTech services in Pakistan is positively associated with higher levels of financial inclusion and economic growth.

Hypothesis 2: A more favorable regulatory environment for FinTech in Pakistan is positively associated with higher levels of financial inclusion and economic growth.

Hypothesis 3: Higher levels of digital literacy among individuals and businesses in Pakistan are positively associated with greater adoption and usage of FinTech services, which in turn is positively associated with higher levels of financial inclusion and economic growth.

2.4. Contribution of the Study

The study could provide insights into the impact of FinTech adoption on financial inclusion and economic growth in Pakistan, which could be useful for policymakers, financial institutions, and FinTech companies operating in the country. By identifying the factors that drive FinTech adoption and usage, the study could help these stakeholders design and implement more effective policies and products to promote financial inclusion and support economic growth. The study could contribute to a better understanding of the regulatory environment for FinTech in Pakistan and its impact on financial inclusion and economic growth. By identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the regulatory framework, the study could inform efforts to improve the regulatory landscape and promote a more conducive environment for FinTech innovation. The study could shed light on the role of digital literacy in promoting FinTech adoption and usage in Pakistan, and provide recommendations for addressing digital literacy gaps to support financial inclusion and economic growth. This could be particularly relevant in the context of Pakistan, where many individuals lack access to formal financial services and may need additional support to fully benefit from FinTech solutions.

To conclude, this literature review has illuminated several facets of development, sustainability, and policy interventions from various studies. These studies combine empirical data with theoretical frameworks to help policymakers create evidence-based solutions to complicated socioeconomic and environmental concerns.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table 1 lists the variables used in this study, along with their symbols, units, and expected theoretical effects.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variable	Symbols	Variables	Definitions
GDP per capita	GDP	Annual %	GDP is an indicator of how much money was created in a nation inside its borders in a given time frame, often a year.
Fintech Adoption	FT	Number of users	Subscription services that offer improve security features and protections for internet users are often referred to as secure internet subscriptions. These services work to

Variable	Symbols	Variables	Definitions
			protect consumer's online activities, private data, and gadgets against a variety of risks including identity theft, cyberattacks, and data breaches.
Financial inclusion	FI	Bank credit to private sector and insurance and financial services.	Domestic credit to the private sector is the term used to describe financial resources given to the private sector by financial institutions, such as through loans, the acquisition of no equity securities, trade credits, and other accounts receivable that create a claim for repayment.
Regulation environment	RE	Regulatory quality (-2.5 to 2.5)	Regulatory quality measures how well the public believes the government can create and carry out sensible laws and rules that support and encourage the growth of the private sector.
Infrastructure	ICTs	ICTs export (%)	The value of each country's ICTs goods exports is goods exports to determine the ICTs good exports as a percentage of total goods exports. The value is then converted to a percentage by multiplying.
Digital literacy	DL	Adult literacy rate (%)	The percentage of adults over the age of 15 who can read and write while comprehending a brief, straight forward statement about their daily lives. Literacy typically includes numeracy. This is the capacity to do basic mathematical operations.
Other variable	EDU	Secondary education and urbanization	People moves from rural to urban regions, which causes urbanization.

Source: World Bank (2023).

3.2 Data Source and Time Period

In this study, we used the quarterly data from 1996Q1 to 2022Q4 and collected the data from the World Development Indicator (2022) and World Government Indicator (2022).

3.3. Econometric Framework

3.3.1 ADF Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is a statistical method used to determine a time series data set is stationary or not. Stationarity is a crucial concept in time series analysis, as it implies that the statistical properties of the data do not change over

time. The ADF test essentially tests the null hypothesis that a unit root is present in a time series against the alternative hypothesis that the series is stationary after differencing it a certain number of times. If the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, it suggests that the time series is non-stationary, whereas rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that the series is stationary.

The ADF test statistic is then computed based on the estimated parameters and their standard errors. The critical values of the test statistic are used to determine whether the null hypothesis of a unit root can be rejected at a certain level of significance. If you have a specific time series data set and want to perform an ADF test, you can use statistical software packages like Python's stats models, R's t-series, or other econometrics software that provide implementations of the ADF test, i.e.,

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \sum FT + \beta_2 \sum FI + \beta_3 \sum RE + \beta_4 \sum ICTS + \beta_5 \sum DL + \beta_6 \sum EDU + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where

GDP= dependent variable

FT, FI, RE, ICSTS, DL, EDU = independent variable

$\alpha, \beta,$ = these are the parameter estimates.

ε =error term

3.3.2 ARDL Approach

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach is a method used in econometrics to analyze the long-run relationship between variables in a time series framework. It allows for the estimation of co-integrating relationships among variables that may have both short-run and long-run dynamics. The ARDL model is particularly useful when dealing with non-stationary time series data, as it accommodates variables that may have different orders of integration. This makes it applicable in situations where the variables may be integrated of order one (I(1)), integrated of order zero (I(0)), or a combination of both. The ARDL approach allows for testing the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables by examining the significance of the coefficients associated with the lagged levels of the variables. Co-integration is inferred if the lagged levels of the variables are found to be statistically significant. Once cointegration is established, the long-run relationship can be analyzed, and the short-run dynamics of the model can also be examined through the coefficients associated with the differenced variables. ARDL modelling is commonly employed in macroeconomic analysis, finance, and other fields where understanding the relationship between variables over time is essential. It offers a flexible framework for capturing both short-run and long-run dynamics in a single model.

3.3.3 ARDL-Bounds Testing Approach

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound test approach is a method used to determine the existence of a long-run relationship among variables in a time series framework. It is particularly useful when dealing with mixed-order integrated time series data, where some variables may be integrated of order one (I(1)) and others may be integrated of order zero (I(0)). The ARDL bound test involves estimating two separate autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models one with a lag length chosen based on an assumption of no co-integration and the other with a lag length chosen based on an assumption of co-integration. The F-test is then used to compare the coefficients of the lagged levels of the variables in the two models. The ARDL bound test approach is widely used in econometrics and time series analysis for testing co-integration, particularly when dealing with mixed-order integrated time series data. It provides a robust method for determining the existence of long-run relationships among variables in a flexible and interpretable manner.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. The mean value of GDP across the observations is approximately 1.78. The maximum GDP observed in the data set is approximately 9.86 and the minimum value observed is about -3.56. The Standard Deviation shows the GDP values vary around the mean by approximately 2.30 units. The Skewness distribution of GDP values is slightly positively skewed, indicating a slight tail to the right. The Kurtosis distribution of GDP values is moderately leptokurtic, meaning it has relatively heavy tails and is peaked compared to a normal distribution. The mean value of the FI across the observations is approximately 3.58.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	GDP	FI	FT	ICTS	RE	DL	EDU
Mean	1.777423	3.578173	7.771822	0.219633	-0.671607	52.97937	29.64356
Median	1.642745	3.738385	7.226563	0.170390	-0.652213	54.85776	31.20831
Maximum	9.856583	6.038567	21.87777	0.621387	-0.466432	59.26778	36.02499
Minimum	-3.555715	1.057739	-0.142017	0.061713	-1.080432	41.57832	24.32446
Std. Dev.	2.300043	1.253983	5.926573	0.144520	0.122353	4.857458	4.046646

Methods	GDP	FI	FT	ICTS	RE	DL	EDU
Skewness	0.148501	-0.278699	0.488498	1.515902	-1.053024	-0.859554	-0.193656
Kurtosis	3.291081	2.283232	2.561149	4.313968	4.794141	2.792675	1.494744

The maximum value of the financial index observed is approximately 6.04 and the minimum value of the observed is about 1.06. The Standard Deviation of the financial index values vary around the mean by approximately 1.25 units. The Skewness distribution of financial index values is slightly negatively skewed, indicating a slight tail to the left and the Kurtosis distribution of financial index values is moderately Platy Kurtis, meaning it has relatively lighter tails compared to a normal distribution. The mean value of the FT index across the observations is approximately 7.77. The maximum foreign trade index observed is approximately 21.88 and the minimum foreign trade index observed is about -0.14 its mean the FT have negative effect on the GDP. The Standard Deviation of foreign trade index values varies around the mean by approximately 5.93 units. The Skewness distribution of foreign trade index values is positively skewed, indicating a tail to the right. The kurtosis distribution of foreign trade index values is moderately leptokurtic. The mean value of ICTS across the observations is approximately 0.22. The maximum value of ICTs observed is approximately 0.62 and the minimum value of observed is about 0.06. The standard Deviation of ICTs values vary around the mean by approximately 0.14 units. The skewness distribution of ICTs values is positively skewed, indicating a tail to the right. The kurtosis distribution of ICTs values is highly leptokurtic. The mean value of the RE index across the observations is approximately -0.67. The maximum value of renewable energy index observed is approximately -0.47 and the minimum index observed is about -1.08. The Standard Deviation of renewable energy index values varies around the mean by approximately 0.12 units. The Skewness distribution of renewable energy index values is negatively skewed, indicating a tail to the left. The kurtosis distribution of renewable energy index values is highly leptokurtic. The mean value of DL index across the observations is approximately 52.98. The maximum index observed is approximately 59.27 and the minimum index observed value of DL is about 41.58. The standard deviation index values vary around the mean by approximately 4.86 units. The skewness distribution of digital literacy index values is negatively skewed, indicating a tail to the left and the Kurtosis distribution of digital literacy index values is moderately leptokurtic. The mean value of EDU index across the observations is approximately 29.64. The maximum education index observed is approximately 36.02 and the minimum index observed is about 24.32. The Standard Deviation index values vary around the mean by approximately 4.05 units. The skewness distribution of education index values is negatively skewed, indicating a tail to the left. The kurtosis distribution of index values is platykurtic. Table 3 shows the correlation matrix estimates.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Probability	GDP	FI	FT	ICTS	RE	DL	EDU
GDP	1						
FI	0.245910	1					
	0.0119	-----					
FT	0.253652	0.582950	1				
	0.0094	0.0000	-----				
ICTS	0.272556	0.394421	-0.057395	1			
	0.0051	0.0000	0.5628	-----			
RE	-0.16526	0.277041	-0.024072	0.440593	1		
	0.0936	0.0044	0.8084	0.0000	-----		
DL	0.232895	0.647930	0.837096	0.119836	-0.014988	1	
	0.0174	0.0000	0.0000	0.2256	0.8800	-----	
EDU	0.220310	0.788843	0.817180	0.249293	0.283552	0.867851	1
	0.0246	0.0000	0.0000	0.0107	0.0035	0.0000	-----

The correlation between "GDP" and "FI" is shows the p-value is 0.245910, and the F-value is 0.0119it indicating a relatively weak positive linear relationship between GDP and the Financial Inclusion. The correlation between FT and GDP is shows with the p-value is 0.253652, and the F-value is 0.0094 represent the positive relationship between them when the Fintech increase the GDP also increase its mean it have positively affected on our economy growth. The correlation between "FT" and "FI" p-value is 0.582950, and the F-value is 0.0000 indicating a moderately strong positive linear relationship between Fintech and the Financial Inclusion. The correlation between "ICTs" and "GDP" P-value is 0.272556, and the F-value is 0.0051. Its mean they have positively relationship on the economic growth. The correlation between "ICTs" and "FI" P-value is 0.394421 and the F-value is 0.0000 its shows the positively relationship between them on the other hand the "ICTs" and "FT" have P-value is -0.057395 and the F-value is 0.5628 its means they have negatively correlate with them. The correlation between "RE" and "FI" P-value is 0.277041 and the F-value is 0.0044 they are positively correlate with them. The correlation between "RE" and "FT" is -0.057395, indicating a very weak negative

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linear relationship between Renewable Energy and Fintech. The correlation between “RE” and “ICTs” P-value 0.440593 and F-value is 0.0000 which mean they have positively correlated. The correlation between “DL” and “GDP” P-value is 0.232895 and F-value is 0.0174. “DL and “FI” P-value is 0.647930 and F-value is 0.0174. The correlation between “DL” and “FT” P-value is 0.837096 and F-value is 0.0000. The correlation between “DL” and “ICTs” P-value is 0.119836 and F-value is 0.2256. “DL” is positively correlated with GDP, FI, FT, and ICTs. The correlation between “EDU” and “GDP” P-value is 0.220310 and F-value is 0.0246. The education is positively correlated with GDP, FI, FT, ICTs, RE, and DL. Correlation values closer to 1 or -1 indicate stronger relationships, while values closer to 0 indicate weaker relationships. The significance level is shows below the correlation coefficients represent the p-values associated with each correlation. These p-values indicate the statistical significance of the correlation coefficient. Correlations with p-values less than a preferred significance level (0.05) are considered statistically significant. Table 4 shows the unit root estimates.

Table 4: Unit Root Test Estimates

Variables	Level	First Difference	Decision
GDP	-4.202***	-2.669	I(0)
FI	-2.019	-2.993*	I(1)
ICTS	-2.536	-3.205*	I(1)
RE	-3.136	-3.745**	I(1)
DL	-4.177***	-3.655**	I(0)
EDU	-2.589	-3.533**	I(1)

Note: *, **, and *** indicates 10%, 5%, and 1% significance level.

GDP is stationary at the Level where the value is -4.202 – This denotes the test statistic for the unit root test at the level of GDP. At the First Difference the GDP value is -2.669 - This represents the test statistic for the unit root test after differencing GDP once. The level test is significant and the first difference test is not significant, it recommends that GDP is stationary at levels I (0). The FI value at Level is -2.019 and the First Difference value is -2.993*. The variable FI is stationary at the first difference I(1) at the 10% level, indicating that FI becomes stationary after differencing once. ICTS is stationary at the First Difference the value of first difference is -3.205. It shows the 1st difference stationary variable I(1) ICTS becomes stationary after differencing once. RE is stationary at the First Difference the value at first difference is -3.745.the variable RE becomes stationary after differencing once. DL is stationary at the level where the value is at Level is -4.177***. This variable DL is stationary at level I(0) so(I(0)), it indicated by the significant level test. The variable EDU is stationary at the First Difference which value is -3.533**. At the I(1) the EDU becomes stationary after differencing once. Table 5 shows the lag length selection criteria.

Table 5: Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-846.5518	NA	0.124580	17.78233	17.96931	17.85791
1	178.6358	1879.511	1.84e-10	-2.554912	-1.059042	-1.950257
2	359.9035	305.8892	1.19e-11	-5.310489	-2.505733*	-4.176761
3	388.1464	43.54118	1.90e-11	-4.878050	-0.764408	-3.215248
4	409.3240	29.56047	3.67e-11	-4.298417	1.124111	-2.106543
5	668.5166	323.9907	5.26e-13	-8.677429	-1.946015	-5.956482
6	770.7191	112.8485*	2.14e-13*	-9.785814*	-1.745514	-6.535793*
7	801.1000	29.11509	4.32e-13	-9.397917	-0.048731	-5.618824
8	842.1327	33.33900	8.10e-13	-9.231930	1.426142	-4.923763

Note: * indicates optimal lag length.

The results show that SC is comparable for the selection of 2nd lag is optimum for the ARDL criteria and the value of 2nd lag in SC is -2.505733* to AIC, but there is a higher consequence for more factors, predominantly for lower sample sizes. It seeks to identify the most efficient model that appropriately fits the facts. Like AIC, lower SC values suggest better model fit. The latency rises SC typically reduces implying a better model fit with greater interruptions. Table 6 shows the ARDL estimates.

Table 6: ARDL Estimates

Dependent Variable: GDP				
Selected Model: ARDL(2, 0, 2, 2, 1, 2, 2)				
Co-integrating Form				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(GDP(-1))	0.898387	0.064223	13.988501	0.0000
D(FI)	-0.077389	0.078326	-0.988034	0.3260
D(FT)	1.055943	0.511575	2.064099	0.0421
D(FT(-1))	-1.012657	0.496246	-2.040637	0.0444

Dependent Variable: GDP				
Selected Model: ARDL(2, 0, 2, 2, 1, 2, 2)				
Co-integrating Form				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(ICTS)	-6.328755	2.689547	-2.353093	0.0210
D(ICTS(-1))	3.551419	2.166250	1.639432	0.1049
D(RE)	2.482823	1.608417	1.543644	0.1264
D(DL)	-0.497000	0.081618	-6.089362	0.0000
D(DL(-1))	0.407138	0.078258	5.202487	0.0000
D(EDU)	0.525171	0.124703	4.211380	0.0001
D(EDU(-1))	-0.450527	0.115193	-3.911069	0.0002
CointEq(-1)	-0.095613	0.026211	-3.647848	0.0005
Long Run Coefficients				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FI	-0.809402	0.880210	-0.919556	0.3604
FT	0.424686	0.244888	1.734205	0.0866
ICTS	5.764847	4.829599	1.193649	0.2360
RE	-14.809614	7.388438	-2.004431	0.0482
DL	-0.819113	0.365158	-2.243174	0.0275
EDU	1.024328	0.516881	1.981746	0.0507
C	12.497769	11.435876	1.092856	0.2776

The substantial positive association between FinTech innovation and GDP growth shows its economic power. Financial technology (FinTech) initiatives boost investment, simplify financial processes, and increase access to money, making economic transactions, entrepreneurship, and financial services innovation simpler. New financial technology platforms boost market liquidity, lower transaction costs, and simplify resource allocation. Countries that use FinTech technology may have better financial intermediation, more efficient markets, and quicker economic growth. However, the complicated relationship between ICT services and GDP shows the positives and downsides of technological growth. Expanding access to ICT boosts productivity, connection, and knowledge exchange. The drawbacks of this trend include structural changes in traditional economic sectors and employment losses. Regulatory frameworks, infrastructural investments, and technological absorptive capacities impact how much ICT services affect GDP, further complicating its relationship with economic growth. The importance of digital literacy in the digital age cannot be overstated. It directly affects GDP, making human capital development a crucial aspect of economic growth. As knowledge-based economies continue to grow, digital literacy becomes a key determinant of economic competitiveness, worker engagement, and innovation. However, regional and demographic differences in digital literacy increase inequalities and hinder fair economic growth. Therefore, authorities must prioritize digital literacy initiatives and educational activities to harness the revolutionary potential of digital technology fully.

Yoon et al. (2023) highlight FinTech's beneficial impact on GDP growth. Additionally, Fidan and Tuğba (2023) demonstrate FinTech's revolutionary impact on financial models and economic growth in seven nations. Oliinyk (2023) found that the involvement of ICT services in the market affects economic indices differently in each country. Although complicated, imports and exports of information and communication technology services show a negative association with GDP fluctuations. The digital economy has immense potential, but Rehman and Nunziante (2023) warn that it may hurt GDP trends. In their research of DL's influence, Wardana et al. (2023) noted that one needs to navigate digital environments carefully to realize its revolutionary potential. Kadir et al. (2023) agree, emphasizing its importance for long-term economic growth. Despite environmental impacts, energy efficiency is essential for economic growth. Ruzima and Veerachamy (2023) emphasize the link between investment in human capital and long-term financial performance, highlighting education as a growth engine for the economy. Bing's (2023) study emphasizes universities' role in high-quality economic development, particularly in the digital sector.

The results show the complex link between technical advancement, human capital development, environmental sustainability, and economic growth, showing how policy interventions may affect global economic patterns. By basing their policy frameworks on sound economic rationales and empirical research, national governments may better navigate current economic conditions and promote inclusive, resilient, and sustainable development.

Table 7 shows the ARDL Bounds testing estimates and confirmed that the variables are cointegrated in the long-run, as F-statistics value fall in the upper bound of 5% significance level. Hence, the estimates are reliable and policy implications can be suggested for long-term impacts for the economy.

Table 7: ARDL-Bounds Estimates

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	4.013063	6
Significance	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
2.5%	2.75	3.99
1%	3.15	4.43

The ARDL bound test is used to determine the presence of long-run relationships among the variables in an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. It measures the coefficients on lagged variables in the model are co-operatively equal to zero, indicating the absence of long-run relationships. F-statistic is the test that used in the ARDL bound test. It measures the overall significance of the lagged variables in the model. The F-statistic value is 4.013063. The critical values are thresholds used to determine the statistical significance of the F-statistic. They depend on the sample size and are used to compare against the calculated F-statistic to determine whether it falls within a certain range of significance. Significance levels typically denoted as α , represent the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is actually true. In your case, the significance levels are given as 10%, 5%, 2.5%, and 1%. These represent common thresholds for determining statistical significance. The critical values corresponding to each significance level are provided in the table. I_0 Bound and I_1 Bound represent the critical values for the F-statistic at different significance levels. I_0 Bound corresponds to the lower bound critical value, and I_1 Bound corresponds to the upper bound critical value. The test statistic must fall between these bounds for a significance level for the null hypothesis to be rejected. The ARDL bound test results, compare the calculated F-statistic to the critical values at the desired significance level. If the calculated F-statistic exceeds the upper bound (I_1 Bound) for a given significance level, the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship is rejected at that significance level. This indicates the presence of long-run relationships among the variables. The calculated F-statistic falls below the lower bound (I_0 Bound) for a given significance level, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, suggesting the absence of long-run relationships. If the calculated F-statistic falls between the I_0 Bound and I_1 Bound, the test results are inconclusive, and the presence of long-run relationships cannot be determined at the specified significance level.

The ARDL bound test helps determine whether there are significant long-run relationships among the variables in the model. It provides valuable insights into the dynamic interactions among the variables over time, aiding in economic analysis and forecasting. The ARDL bound test is a useful tool for assessing the presence of long-run relationships in ARDL models, helping researchers and policymakers understand the underlying dynamics of the economic system under study.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study illustrates the complex link between FinTech, financial inclusion, and Pakistani economic development. This study seeks to understand how FinTech innovations may solve systemic financial marginalization and reshape Pakistan's economy. The results not only illuminate FinTech's multifaceted impact on Pakistan's economy using econometric models and empirical research but also underscore the power of education. FinTech's ability to increase capital access, entrepreneurialism, and inclusive economic growth is making it an essential economic element. The research highlights the importance of education to Pakistan's economic growth, empowering the nation to harness its human capital for economic prosperity. Conversely, the study shows how regulatory frameworks, digital literacy, and ICT affect Pakistan's economic progress. The study reveals that digital literacy affects FinTech adoption and acceptance. It also demonstrates digital literacy disparities, which may worsen inequalities and impede FinTech from properly advancing the economy. The study underlines the necessity for robust regulatory frameworks that foster innovation, protect consumers, and ensure financial stability. This reassures the audience that regulatory frameworks are in place to manage the potential risks of FinTech adoption and drive positive economic outcomes.

This study has significant policy consequences; it gives a roadmap for equitable economic growth and addresses Pakistan's long-standing financial exclusion issues via FinTech. These policy recommendations emphasize FinTech's role in expanding financial services, promoting economic activity, and empowering individuals from all backgrounds. Policymakers should prioritize creating a regulatory environment that fosters innovation, protects consumers, and maintains financial stability. FinTech solutions must be responsibly implemented by simplifying licensing procedures, standardizing regulatory frameworks, and strengthening supervisory powers. Legislation that gives market actors confidence may boost FinTech startup investment, innovation, and

financial inclusion channels. For improved technology absorption and digital inclusiveness, governments should fund digital literacy initiatives and infrastructure. Policies that promote inexpensive internet, digital literacy, and technological skills may assist communities and people in overcoming financial problems. This will improve FinTech usage by communities and people, closing the digital gap. FinTech innovation and financial service development need public-private partnerships and cooperation, which must be supported. Policymakers may increase financial inclusion and economic resilience by encouraging innovation ecosystems, information sharing, and industry cooperation to build FinTech solutions for disadvantaged people. Policymakers should prioritize education and human capital for citizens to participate in the digital economy. Governments should update educational curricula, improve vocational training, and support lifelong learning to prepare the workforce for FinTech advancements and promote inclusive growth, innovation, and economic productivity. Lawmakers should consider FinTech, financial inclusion, and socioeconomic development goals while making legislation. Policymakers can ensure that FinTech ventures reduce poverty, alter the financial industry, and earn money. This allows FinTech issues to be included in national and sustainable development strategies.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the necessity for coordinated and proactive policies to leverage FinTech's revolutionary capacity for fair economic development in Pakistan. Policymakers can strengthen inclusive and prosperous financial ecosystems for everyone by prioritizing regulatory changes, investing in digital infrastructure and literacy programs, encouraging innovative ecosystems, and supporting human capital development.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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